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An Empirical Roofline Model for Extreme-Scale I/O Workload Analysis

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Abstract—Since the performance of an application in modern HPC and supercomputing systems is not only limited by computations and memory accesses, new techniques are needed to characterize the performance of the system or application. In this preliminary work, we propose an empirical Roofline model and corresponding workflow for I/O workload analysis that can be adapted in the future for a multidimensional score, allowing to characterize application performance for different HPC systems. Regarding the I/O aspect, our empirical Roofline model focuses on the most commonly used performance metrics, I/O operations per second (IOPS) and I/O bandwidth. By applying the Roofline modeling, the I/O performance of an application can be intuitively characterized and possible performance bottlenecks can be identified without any deeper knowledge of the I/O stack. Providing a case study based on different application I/O kernels, we demonstrate that our empirical Roofline model is suitable to characterize the performance for a variety of applications.

Index Terms—I/O, HPC, Performance Modeling Workflow, I/O Analysis, I/O Performance, I/O System Evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of the exascale era and the need to support more diverse and complex scientific workloads, the components of HPC and supercomputing systems are becoming more and more heterogeneous and modular [1], [2]. While compute units are optimized for specific applications and their processing power is steadily increasing, the diversity of workloads is also increasing, making I/O behavior and access patterns even less predictable [3]. Furthermore, as the scale of HPC systems grows proportionally and applications become more data-intensive, accurate modeling of I/O performance becomes increasingly complex. Given the growing gap between compute performance and I/O capacity, existing approaches to performance modeling need to be extended to account for additional factors such as memory, I/O, and network [4], [5]. In addition, performance modeling techniques should be intuitive so that users without prior knowledge can understand the resulting performance [6], [7].

A promising approach for node-level performance characterization is the *Roofline model*. This model was introduced in 2009 by Williams et al. [6] as a visual method for understanding the performance capabilities and limitations of parallel computing systems and identifying potential bottlenecks. As shown in Figure 1, the Roofline model represents the performance of a system by plotting the operational intensity (FLOPS/byte) of a computation on the x-axis and the achievable performance (FLOPS) on the y-axis. Based on

Fig. 1: Example of a naïve Roofline Model [6].

bound and bottleneck analysis [8], Williams et al. specify the upper bound on achievable performance for a given computer as shown in Equation 1.

$$\text{Attainable GFlops/sec} = \text{Min}(\text{Peak Floating Point Performance,}$$

$$\text{Peak Memory Bandwidth} \times \text{Operational intensity}) \quad (1)$$

For operational intensity (defined in Equation 2), the ratio of floating-point operations to the total memory traffic is used, which corresponds to the ratio of computation work to communication work. One can think of it as a column that reaches to the ceiling. When it hits the flat part of the ceiling, the performance is limited by the computational power, i.e., *compute-bound*. However, if it hits the slanted part of the ceiling, this is an indication that the performance is limited by the memory, i.e., *memory-bound*.

$$\text{Operational intensity} = \frac{\text{Floating point operations}}{\text{Memory bytes transferred}} \quad (2)$$

While the peak performance of each dimension in the Roofline model is determined on the system side by specific benchmarks such as STREAM [9] or hardware specifications, the operational intensity is usually determined by algorithmic

analysis. As the roofline curve illustrates the theoretical peak performance of the system in terms of memory bandwidth and computational power, the ridge point where the diagonal and horizontal ceilings intersect provides insights into the overall performance of the system.

Considering the increasingly heterogeneous system resources and complexity of emerging workloads, the underlying I/O resources need to be better understood in order to be utilized more efficiently. Therefore, we propose an extension of the naïve Roofline model to also include I/O characterization and make the following contributions:

- An *empirical Roofline model* that can be used to analyze I/O workload at a large scale and provides the foundation for a multidimensional evaluation (i.e., score) for system and application characterization.
- A *generic workflow* with a corresponding tool for the roofline analysis, i.e., system-specific performance can be derived automatically from IOR [10] and presented as the roofline in a visualization. In addition, application-specific I/O performance can be automatically extracted from Darshan [11] outputs and displayed in the model.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. IO500 Benchmark

The IO500 benchmark [12] is an established I/O benchmark method for measuring the performance of parallel file systems. It can be used to determine performance limits for optimized and suboptimal applications. The benchmark assesses the performance of parallel file systems using a set of predefined workloads that include both small and large file operations, as well as various I/O patterns such as sequential and random accesses. In addition to data test cases, it includes test cases for metadata operations that measure the performance of file system metadata operations. Based on IOR and MD-Test [10], the benchmark produces a single score, known as the IO500 score, which is intended to provide a quick and easy way to compare the performance of different systems.

B. User-Centric System Fault Identification using IO500

A method for predicting I/O performance and providing realistic expectations for users was proposed by Liem et al. [13] in their IO500-based workflow. This approach utilizes the IO500 benchmark to identify potential performance bottlenecks and suggests optimization strategies for the user’s specific application. The four benchmark scenarios of IO500 (IOR-hard, IOR-easy, mdtest-hard, and mdtest-easy) are used to create a two-dimensional bounding box for user expectation. By comparing I/O performance of the application with the bounding box, use cases such as performance assessment and anomaly detection can be covered.

C. An Extended Roofline Model with Communication-Awareness for Distributed-Memory HPC Systems

Accounting for communication costs is essential to describe the system behavior of modern HPC and supercomputing systems as accurately as possible. To predict the performance of

parallel programs on systems with distributed memory, Cardwell and Song [5] extend the classic Roofline performance model to include communication costs in addition to memory access and CPU performance. For the communication-aware Roofline model, the so-called communication arithmetic intensity is calculated as follow:

$$\text{Operational Intensity} = \frac{\text{Floating point operations}}{\text{Network bytes transferred}} \quad (3)$$

Regarding the upper limit for the attainable performance in terms of GFLOPS/s, the following formula is used:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Attainable Performance} = \text{Min}(\text{Peak Floating Point Performance,} \\ \text{Peak Communication Bandwidth} \\ \times \text{Communication Arithmetic Intensity}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

To determine the peak communication performance, the microbenchmark Ping-Pong is used in addition to the original approach. Furthermore, through the experiments conducted, the authors were able to show that the extended model is suitable to evaluate the performance for different applications on various distributed memory systems. Since the extended model is three-dimensional, both 2D and 3D visualizations can be created, with the 2D visualization consisting of two separate representations: network and memory. Because this representation deviates from the original Roofline model, Checconi et al. [14] introduce the Ridgeline model. This approach allows roofline plots for multiple resources to be displayed in an intuitive planar diagram, identifying bottlenecks to peak kernel or application performance in a conventional way.

D. Discussion

Like Top500 [15], [16], IO500 is a standardized method for evaluating systems in terms of I/O performance. However, it should be noted that the IO500 score is not a perfect metric and has some limitations. One limitation is that the IO500 score does not have a dimension such as GFLOPS for Top500. Basically, the score value consists of the geometric mean of different test cases, where the units of the data and metadata test cases are blended, i.e., GiB/s and KIOPS. In addition, the IO500 focuses on a specific set of workloads and parallel file systems and therefore may not be representative of all possible workloads and types of storage systems. Since the proposed bounding box approach is limited to IO500, it is not compatible with other applications or benchmarks.

To provide an accurate user expectation for future workloads, an approach should be flexible to cover more I/O patterns. Roofline modeling is a powerful technique for node-level performance modeling and can be extended to other domains. However, with the changing landscape of emerging hybrid HPC workloads and the ever increasing gap between the compute and storage performance capabilities, I/O performance is increasingly the limiting factor for the overall performance. Accordingly, the applicability of roofline techniques to I/O characterization must also be explored.

III. EMPIRICAL I/O ROOFLINE MODEL

To better understand the I/O of emerging workloads and to provide a more comprehensive characterization of HPC systems and implement a consistent scoring model in the future, we have adopted the classic Roofline model for I/O workload analysis. Our model provides a basic understanding of how close observed I/O performance is to peak performance and can also be used to identify performance bottlenecks.

A. The I/O Roofline Model

As pointed out in the discussion of related work in Section II, the intuitive Roofline model can be adapted as needed and extended with appropriate metrics. However, the model is fundamentally based on looking at the relationship between work and traffic, where work is a quantitative concept and traffic is the amount of data required to do the work. Because applications for HPC systems result from various workloads in different domains, optimal performance does not necessarily mean that an application must both compute a lot and perform a lot of I/O. Accordingly, an application can either be compute-intensive or I/O-intensive. Therefore, the consideration of floating point operation to I/O bandwidth is irrelevant for the analysis of I/O performance.

To tailor the model for characterizing I/O performance, our I/O Roofline model is based on the most widely accepted performance metric for I/O, i.e., IOPS and the corresponding bandwidth. IOPS measure the number of reads and writes that a storage system can perform per second. The metric indicates how many operations the storage system can handle within a fixed period of time, which is important for applications that require a large number of small operations. Regarding the I/O stack, the I/O operations on each layer are different. In this work, we focus on POSIX and MPI-IO, therefore the I/O operations of both layers can be examined. Throughput, on the other hand, measures the total amount of data that can be read or written per second. It reflects the bandwidth of the storage system, which is important for applications where large amounts of data need to be transferred quickly, such as scientific simulations and training phases for machine learning. The upper bound for the attainable performance in terms of IOPS is defined by Equation 5 for the Roofline model.

$$\text{Attainable Performance} = \text{Min}(\text{Peak IOPS}, \text{Peak I/O Bandwidth} \times \text{I/O Intensity}) \quad (5)$$

Instead of the classical operational intensity and peak memory bandwidth, we use *I/O intensity* and peak I/O bandwidth for the Roofline model. Considering the different definitions of I/O intensity [17]–[19], our definition of I/O intensity corresponds to the total number of I/O operations (IOP) per bytes read and written, as shown in Equation 6.

$$\text{I/O Intensity} = \frac{\text{Total I/O Operations}}{(\text{Read Bytes} + \text{Write Bytes})} \quad (6)$$

A common observation with applications that are not optimized for I/O is that these applications make optimal use of computing resources, but over time perform a large number of

Parameter	Dim.	Derivation	Specificity
Peak IOPS	$\frac{\text{IOP}}{\text{s}}$	Benchmark	System-specific
Peak I/O Bandwidth	$\frac{\text{Byte}}{\text{s}}$	Benchmark	System-specific
I/O Intensity	$\frac{\text{IOP}}{\text{Byte}}$	Characterization	Application-specific

TABLE I: Parameters for the empirical I/O Roofline model.

small I/O operations, which is not optimal for the underlying I/O and storage system resources. Considering this observation, I/O intensity can be a valuable metric as it indicates the ratio between the I/O operations performed and the total amount of data of an application during its runtime. As a result, we have gained a new qualitative dimension for the evaluation of I/O performance with the unit IOP/byte, which at the same time has a physical meaning.

B. Workflow for the I/O Roofline Analysis

Based on the previously defined attainable performance and I/O intensity, three parameters are needed to create a Roofline model. As shown in Table I, the parameters can be divided into two categories, i.e., system-specific and application-specific. Depending on the category, the parameters can be derived in different ways. Peak performance can usually be determined either theoretically, i.e., via the hardware specification, or empirically via benchmarks. Since the theoretical determination of peak performance requires expertise from various areas such as the network, file systems, storage hardware itself, and is also extremely time-consuming, the empirical approach is a better alternative for users with less experience and limited resources. Therefore, in this paper, we limit ourselves to determining the peak performance based on community benchmarks.

The I/O intensity is an application-specific parameter which describes the relationship between the number of I/O operations and the amount of bytes read and written. This parameter can also be determined in two ways, mainly by measurements or by analysis of the code. Since the latter is not suitable for complex applications in practice, we propose to derive the application-specific parameter from a low-overhead characterization tool instead of a tracing tool. The workflow and the Roofline model itself are tool-agnostic and therefore not limited to specific benchmarks or tools for deriving the parameters. Hence, the workflow can be adjusted as needed for the analysis. Since IOR offers the ability to mimic different I/O patterns through various APIs such as HDF5, MPI-IO, POSIX, it is a popular choice for I/O performance evaluation and adopted for IO500 ranking. Another widely used tool is Darshan, which provides the ability to characterize the I/O behavior of an application with little overhead. For demonstration purposes, IOR and Darshan are applied for deriving the parameters in this work. However, Darshan can also determine system-specific parameters for applications or benchmarks.

As Figure 2 indicates, the starting point for the I/O Roofline analysis is to perform benchmark and application I/O characterization. IOR provides both the bandwidth and the number of IOPS for a given I/O pattern for a given system so that

Fig. 2: Workflow of ERT4IO.

the resulting performance can be applied directly. In addition to using IOR, these parameters can be determined especially by combining Darshan with any application or benchmark. In contrast, the output of Darshan is not suitable for direct use because the required information needs to be filtered and aggregated first, e.g., the number of I/O operations and the amount of data read and written.

To automate our workflow and finally visualize the resulting Roofline model, the Python-based tool *ERT4IO* (Empirical Roofline Tool for I/O) has been implemented. By specifying the output paths and interface such as POSIX or MPI-IO, both the system-specific and application-specific parameters are extracted. With the extracted parameters, a corresponding Roofline model is created and visualized with ERT4IO. In addition, we plan to preserve the Roofline model in a database that will allow us to perform Roofline analysis in our modular and automated workload analysis framework MAWA-HPC [7] in the future and thus share the knowledge gained with the HPC community. Various use cases can be covered by the visualization. For example, systems with different configurations and hardware can be compared and evaluated. It also provides users with an intuitive way to get an estimate of their application’s I/O performance, which can be helpful in identifying performance bottlenecks.

IV. CASE STUDY

To illustrate the applicability of the I/O Roofline model, case studies are conducted on the FUCHS-CSC at Goethe University Frankfurt using different benchmarks and applications.

A. Test Environment

The FUCHS-CSC cluster [20] provides a total of 198 nodes, each equipped with 2x Intel Xeon E5-2670 v2 and 128 GB RAM. Since each node offers 20 cores, 3960 cores can be allocated. In addition, FUCHS-CSC supports BeeGFS as parallel file system and through InfiniBand (FDR). For the case study, we use the NAS Parallel Benchmarks (NPB) [21], [22] and Hardware Accelerated Cosmology Code (HACC)-IO [23], [24] as application kernels, and IOR to drive the system-specific parameters. HACC-IO is based on N-body techniques

to simulate the formation of structure in the universe. Therefore, I/O patterns, including checkpoint and restart, various I/O interfaces and file access patterns such as single shared file, file per process are captured by HACC-IO. NPB consist of a set of programs and is typically used to evaluate the performance of parallel supercomputers. It comes from CFD applications, which include 5 kernels and 3 pseudo-applications.

B. Applicability to the Evaluation of Applications

In the first case, we are interested in whether the applications characterized by Darshan are correctly represented in the Roofline model. Our goal is to support different layers of the parallel I/O stack for Roofline analysis in the future. Therefore, we first create our model for the two interfaces POSIX and MPI-IO. Since the case study is not about determining peak performance, we assume that the peak performance can be achieved with the IO500-Easy test case and 400 processes. In addition to IOR, HACC-IO and the I/O kernel for block tri-diagonal solver of NPB are used to present a POSIX and MPI-IO application, respectively. To illustrate the difference between peak performance and application performance, both applications are run with up to 100 processes, i.e., -n100.

Fig. 3: Empirical Roofline analysis for FUCHS-CSC.

As depicted in Figure 3, a separate roofline is generated for each I/O interface, i.e., orange for POSIX and blue for MPI-IO. While the peak performance for POSIX is 10126.58 MiB/s and 10151.89 IOPS, MPI-IO achieves a peak performance of 6666 MiB/s and 3365 IOPS. The applications and IOR executed with fewer processes are shown as colored dots and do not exceed the corresponding peak performance. Our illustration clearly shows that applications with different I/O patterns and problem sizes result in different I/O intensities.

Since IOR is used to generate the roofline for both I/O interfaces, additional IOR runs with fewer processes are in parallel under the corresponding ridge points, showing the same I/O intensity with different peak IOPS. The reason for this is that for the file-per-process pattern IOR increases the

amount of data with increasing number of processes, so the problem size scales with the number of processes. Depending on the problem size, the underlying resources can process different numbers of I/O operations per second.

Similar phenomena can be observed with HACC-IO, such that the application workload scales linearly with the number of processes. However, while the I/O intensity of IOR and HACC-IO remains constant with increasing processes, the I/O intensity of NPB increases. Since the problem size does not change for NPB, the amount of read and write data remains the same for any number of processes. In addition to the constant problem size, NPB also uses MPI-IO collective I/O instead of the file-per-process pattern used by IOR and HACC-IO.

This case demonstrated the applicability of the I/O Roofline model. On the one hand, the necessary parameters can be extracted from characterization tools such as Darshan as well as from benchmarks. On the other hand, the I/O performance of different applications can be mapped to our model and the defined parameters can be characterized.

C. Applicability to the Evaluation of Systems

In this case, we are concerned with the comparability of systems in terms of I/O performance. Therefore, we are interested in whether the I/O Roofline model is suitable for evaluating different systems. To cover this case study, the Cesari cluster is included as a reference system. Similar to the FUCHS-CSC cluster, Cesari also supports InfiniBand (FDR) and provides 20 cores each node, i.e., dual socket Intel Xeon E5-2660 v2. However, Cesari is much smaller in scale and does not provide access to a parallel file system.

Fig. 4: Roofline model comparison for multiple systems.

The Roofline model for evaluating system performance is shown in Figure 4. Two test systems were tested with identical I/O access patterns as described in Section IV-B and up to 100 processes. The results show that peak performance was achieved with different number of processes, with 7619 MiB/s and 7638 IOPS on the FUCHS-CSC cluster at maximum

Fig. 5: Integration of the I/O Roofline model into a modular and automated analysis framework.

processes, and 1000 MiB/s and 1024 IOPS on Cesari with minimum processes. Therefore, the peak performance of the FUCHS-CSC cluster improves as the number of processes increases, while the peak performance of the Cesari cluster decreases as the number of processes increases. As previously noted, Cesari does not rely on a parallel file systems. Therefore, a key indicator for the poor performance on Cesari is the underlying file system, which needs to be further investigated in the future. Since the same I/O pattern was executed with IOR on different systems, the I/O operational intensity for all iterations performed on both systems remains the same. In addition, as mentioned in Section III-B, system-specific parameters are derived from specific benchmarks that are responsible for establishing the roofline. Therefore, the performance evaluation of the I/O systems can be based on the ridge point (RP), i.e., the I/O intensity and IOPS of the corresponding benchmark (e.g., IO500). The advantage is that a score can be derived for a system with a meaningful dimension, thereby improving the comparability of I/O systems.

V. OUTLOOK

Considering our preliminary I/O Roofline model and associated workflow, there is potential for future improvement. The workflow for our I/O Roofline model is tool and platform agnostic, allowing ERT4IO to be extended to support additional profiling and tracing tools and benchmarks. This extension can validate our original model and add support for additional I/O interfaces, such as HDF5 [25] and PnetCDF [26].

To better understand emerging HPC workloads and provide a comprehensive view of application and system performance, a multi-dimensional performance score is planned for the future. Our holistic performance score, as shown in Figure 5, will take into account multiple performance factors such as network, compute power, and parallel I/O. To create a multidimensional performance score, system- and application-specific parameters related to the network and data processing will be automatically collected and incorporated into a multidimensional Roofline model. Based on this model, the score can be derived and then used to easily evaluate the

performance of various systems and applications. In parallel to the presented approach, we are already working on a *Network Performance Collector* (NPC) workflow that will enable automatic characterization of network performance.

In addition, by using multidimensional performance rating and integrating ERT4IO into the MAWA-HPC framework [7], a comprehensive and interactive analysis can be performed for various use cases. For example, user hints such as Drishti [27] as well as bottleneck detection, pattern analysis, and performance prediction can be provided, leading to valuable insights for understanding the performance of emerging workloads.

Finally, to compare two systems in a more fine-grained way, our I/O Roofline model can be extended to the node level with appropriate system characterization in the future.

VI. CONCLUSION

Increasing hardware heterogeneity and emerging workloads make performance modeling for future HPC and supercomputing systems increasingly complex, requiring expertise from multiple domains. To address this challenge and make I/O performance modeling more accessible to users with limited prior knowledge, we propose an empirical Roofline model for I/O in this paper. Our model is based on the established Roofline model and can be intuitively applied to different use cases. Using our workflow and the Python-based tool ERT4IO, the required parameters for the Roofline can be efficiently and automatically extracted from a variety of sources, including benchmarks and Darshan output. Based on the parameters, ERT4IO also provides a convenient way to visualize multiple rooflines and applications in a single plot.

The results of our case study demonstrate the effectiveness of our Roofline model in characterizing I/O performance for a variety of applications and in assessing the performance of different systems. Therefore, we believe that the Roofline model has great potential to be used as a multidimensional performance score for system characterization in the future.

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